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Editorial.....

According to UNESCO education is the basis for sustainable development. Sustainable development has become an important issue on international, national and region agenda concerning education policy over the past few years. Articulating the goals of Higher Education, Radha Krishnan Commission on University Education 1948-49 put it in following words, "The most important and urgent reform needed in higher education is to transform it, to endeavour to relate it to the life, needs and aspirations of the people and thereby make it the powerful instrument of social, economic and cultural transformation necessary for the realization of the national goals." For the purpose, education should be developed so as to increase productivity, achieve social and national integration, accelerate the process of modernization and cultivate social moral and spiritual values. Unfortunately, for the entire program made even 70 years after Indian independence, higher education faces challenges in the critical areas of quality and quantity. Main challenge is huge demand-supply gap, not just in terms of seats available but more so in terms of seats available in institutions who offer quality education. We have to think seriously over it.

I feel great pleasure to present our International Journal "Remarking An Analisation". Like the previous edition this issue also contains good research papers on various areas of research. "Remarking An Analisation" invites original contribution in various branches of social science, science, engineering, management and other.

I am thankful to the members of the editorial Board and Advisory Board for their constant cooperation and guidance. My sincere thanks are also due to authors of various research papers. I hope that in future also the author will continue their support in sending valuable research papers for this journal so that people at large may get new things in the modern era.

Deepti Mishra
Editor

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